

Information sheet regarding the use of personal data

Participation at Living Lab activity within the framework of the Horizon project WoodStock

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Grant Agreement number	101181021
Project title	WoodStock
Start date of the project	01/11/2024
End date of the project	31/10/2028
Project website	https://www.woodstockproject.eu/

Before participating in a stakeholder engagement activity of the WoodStock project in the form of a workshop, a survey and/or an interview, please take the time to read this information letter carefully before you decide to participate in this study. Do not hesitate to ask questions to the researcher if there are any ambiguities or if you would like additional information. Make sure you understand everything. Once you have decided to participate in the study you will be asked to sign the consent form on the last page.

1. Project summary

WoodStock is a project focused on promoting climate-smart wood construction practices in line with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative. It aims to quantify and map wood resources, including under-utilised streams. The research will map the flow of wood material during its life span. This approach provides insights into wood utilisation potential, climate mitigation impacts, and resource availability. Additionally, the project employs a dynamic Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology to evaluate the environmental, social, and economic impacts associated with various resource streams and scenarios.

The project aims to develop zero-waste and circular building designs by leveraging digital twins and involving multiple stakeholders through co-creation activities, following NEB principles in six Living Labs across different European regions. WoodStock also seeks to advance systemic circular solutions for zero-waste and community-based wood construction, aligning novel business strategies with policy recommendations, and conducting demonstration, training, and educational activities to promote climate-smart and sustainable wood use in construction.

Key outcomes of the project include an inspirational guideline document for circular wood use, a WoodBook containing building blueprints adhering to NEB values of beauty, inclusion, and sustainability, and an EU-roadmap for future initiatives. These results will be made available on the European Wood Construction Observatory (EWCO), an AI-powered central hub for best practices, guidelines, and innovative solutions. The EWCO will facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring the project's impact and longevity beyond its initial duration, in alignment with the NEB Academy.

2. Purpose of data collection

If any data is being collected during the activity, this will be used as input to reach the objective of the project, as described in the project summary.

3. Risk of participation

There are no risks foreseen associated with participating in the stakeholder activities of the WoodStock project.

4. Compliance with ethical and legal regulations

The researchers will conduct this study in accordance with accepted standards of scientific and ethical conduct. In doing so, they adhere to the principles of research integrity as described in "The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity" 2 (2017, revised edition, ALLEA) and adopt good research practices.

We comply with EU and national ethical and legal regulations, including the latest GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation 2016/680) framework of the EU.

5. Privacy and data protection

The legal framework for the processing of personal data and confidential information in the context of this study is defined by:

- The European General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 of April 27, 2016, in force since May 25, 2018 (the GDPR);

The following personal data will be processed:

- Surname and first name, postal code, occupation, gender, education, email address
- WoodStock partners may use information on the company, institute, organisation or sector that you are representing, only if this is relevant to the outcome of the project.

For the processing of your personal data, your explicit permission will be asked. This is done by signing a 'consent form'. This consent can be withdrawn at any time by notifying the principal investigator. Data gathered during surveys, interviews and/or interactive workshops can be recorded and stored on secure servers. Data might be processed and analysed for publication in reports, scientific journals and other forms of project outputs. None of the raw data will be transferred to third parties, only anonymised data can be transferred. The retention time of the original data is the same as the project duration, although the anonymised resultant data may be stored for longer periods of time to be used in future research. A copy of informed consent is kept on file for up to three years after

project closure by the data controller, and access can be requested by the research participant.

You have the right to consult the data which have been collected about you and you may also request a copy, as long as this does not violate the rights and freedoms of others. Any incorrect data about you can be corrected at your request. Moreover, you have the right to be forgotten: this means that, after withdrawing your permission, you can ask to have your personal data removed.

To exercise any of the above rights, please contact the project coordinator or the project data controller.

WoodStock project partners and the project management team reserve the right to use any photograph/video taken at any WoodStock event without the expressed and written permission of those included in the photograph/video. Project partners and the project management team may use the photograph/video in publications or other media material produced, used or contracted by WoodStock, including but not limited to: brochures, invitations, books, newspapers, magazines, television, websites, etc.

6. Withdrawal of participation

Participation in this study is completely voluntary and there can be no coercion in any way. You may refuse to participate in the study and you may withdraw from the study at any time without having to provide a reason. If you refuse to participate, or if you decide to withdraw from an ongoing study, this will in no way affect your continued relationship with the investigator. At any point you may withdraw your participation to the event, survey, or interview by emailing your withdrawal request to the project coordinator or the project data controller.

7. Points of contact

Point of contact	Email address
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